

Child Abuse

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Introduction

Childhood is the primary stage of Life. It knows no worry or anxiety, no good or evil. It is the period of both ignorance and innocence. The heart of a child is as pure as a crystal and it is also said that “God lives in a child”

But some people without understanding the importance of the fact that a child is God’s gift, abuse them to the extent that their future is ruined forever. However if they are lucky enough, they are guided by a mentor in the future who changes their view of the world explaining the significance of life and explaining the fact that all individuals are not the same.

Child abuse is a crime which is committed by individuals who are frustrated by their own lives. Abusing a child is as serious crime as killing a person because a child is soft by nature and any abuse that he or she goes through in early stages of life, leaves a lasting imprint on its mind for always.

The moment his memory flashes of the abuses that he or she has faced in their lifetime, however happy that moment might be, the child’s heart is filled with sadness.

However hard the child tries to forget or erase such memories all he or she ends up in is being frustrated. Some of the victims of child abuse lose their confidence forever and lead their lives as introverts.

What do you mean by Child abuse?

The international society for the prevention of Child Abuse of neglect recently compared definitions of Abuse from 58 countries and found some commonality in what was considered abusive. In 1999, the World Health Organisation consultation on child abuse prevention drafted the following definition “Child Abuse or Maltreatment constitutes all forms of physical and/or emotional ill treatment, sexual abuse, neglect or negligent treatment or commercial or other exploitation, resulting in actual or potential harm to the child’s health survival development or dignity in the content of a relationship of responsibility, trust or power.

Child abuse includes both physical as well as verbal abuse. Even when a child is not abused physically, there are cases where he or she is abused verbally constantly. This behaviour affects the mental behaviour of the child to such an extent that at times psychiatrist

help is needed to get them back to normal mental stage. Not only have such children loosed the happiness that every child deserves in childhood but they also fail to understand what happiness means for a child.

There are four types of child maltreatment by caregivers, namely

- Physical abuse
- Sexual abuse
- Emotional abuse or Psychological abuse
- Substance abuse

Physical Abuse

Physical abuse is non-accidental physical injury, burning or otherwise harming a child, that is inflicted by a parent, caregiver or another person who has responsibility for the child. Physical abuse involves physical aggression directed at a child, deliberate infliction of serious injuries or actions that place the child at obvious risk of serious injury or death.

Sexual Abuse

Sexual abuse includes activities by a parent or caregiver such as fondling a child’s genitals penetration, incest, rape, sodomy, indecent exposure and exploitation through prostitution or the production on pornographic materials. Child sexual abuse is a form of child abuse in which an adult or older adolescent abuses a child for sexual stimulation. Sexual abuse is defined “The employment use, persuasion, inducement, enticement or coercion of any child to engage in or assist any other person to engage in any sexually explicit conduct or simulation of such conduct for producing a visual depiction of such conduct or the rape and in cases of caretaker or interfamilial relationships, statutory rape molestation, prostitution or another form of sexual exploitation of children or incest with children”.

Emotional Abuse or Psychological Abuse

It is a pattern of behaviour that impairs a child emotional development or sense of self-worth. This may include constant criticism, threats or rejection, as well as withholding love, support or guidance. Emotional abuse is often difficult to prove and therefore child protective services may not be able to intervene without evidence of harm or mental injury to the child. Spurning, terrorizing, isolating, exploiting, corrupting, denying emotional responsiveness or neglect behaviour or extreme incidents that convey to children that they are worthless, followed, unloved, unwanted, endangered or only of value in meeting another’s needs all come under psychological abuse. Emotional abuse is almost always present when other types of maltreatment are identified.

Substance Abuse

Substance abuse is the use of drugs, alcohol or chemicals. The substance abuse results in physical, psychological emotional harm to the user or others. Parental exposure of a child to harm due to the mother’s use of illegal drug or other substance use of a controlled substance by a caregiver that impairs the caregiver’s ability to adequately care for the child.

The exploitation against the child as follows in the a to z-order:

- ATTACKING
- BRUTALIZING
- CORRUPTING
- DISTURBING
- EVE-TEASING

- FRIGHTENING
 - GLIMMERING
 - HALLUCINATING
 - ISOLATING
 - JOLTING
 - KILLING
 - LIMITING
 - MOLESTING
 - NUDIFYING
 - OBJECTIFYING
 - PRETENDING
 - QUASHING
 - RAPPING
 - SEDUCING, SPURNING
 - TERRORIZING
 - UNDER ESTIMATING
 - VULGARIZING
 - WASTING
 - X-RATING
 - YELLING
 - ZONING
- Into sexual object

Methods of Preventing Child Abuse

- A support group structure is needed to reinforce parenting skills and closely monitor the child's well being.
- Enable the children to differentiate good touch & bad touch children are to be advised that, they should not allow anyone touching them unwontedly and if anyone attempts to touch them, they should report it to their parents and teachers.
- The children who are subjected to family violence and neglect may seek redress by approaching the nearby service organization.
- Those who abuse children including the parents be punished legally, this will make others to restrain from indulging in child abuse.
- Mother should be important factor in preventing child abuse. It is necessary that, Women are better educated before their marriage economically self-sufficient and aware of child-rearing practices.
- Participate in child's activities & get to know child's friends.
- Teach the child to use their voice to allow them to prevent abuse in their own life.
- Listen to them & believe what they say
- Be aware of changes in child's behaviour or attitude and inquire into it.
- Be alert for any talk that reveals premature sexual understanding.
- Pay attention when someone shows greater than normal interest in child.
- Moral education should be taught in schools.
- At the time of recruiting person for employment, their moral standard are also be given due consideration.

Child Labour

Child abuse occurs in various forms. In extreme cases a girl child is found raped, some children are beaten up by their parents and at times school teachers. As a matter of fact, child labour is also a form of continuous child abuse.

At an age when the child should attend school, he or she is forced to work in factories, at workplaces and as domestic help in our houses. If we practice child labour, we are also abusing the child, despite the justification that we are helping the child’s family to earn their daily bread.

Child labour should keep in mind the fact that if we want to abolish child labour from its very roots we should first take oath that we will not employ and child to help us in the domestic purposes.

Conclusion

Childhood is the golden period of life and it is also said that God resides in a child’s heart. Abusing a child is like insulting the God you preach. A child has a soft heart and is free from all kinds of worries and anxieties as a result of which even a little misbehaviour with him leaves a permanent mark in his mind.

The memories of childhood have their own significance in one’s life. As one grows up, one feels more and more attached with his childhood, the best period in an individual’s life. Having no anxieties, worries or work, a child is free from the dirty and filthy noise of the worldly life.

A child’s motto of life is “eat, drink and be merry”. And when the child is abused, it is easy to understand what kind of memories he or she will develop.

The harmful effects of child abuse are essential to be understood by one and all to abolish it completely.

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